

Simulation of Inverter Fed Induction Motor Drive with Labview

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Abstract : This paper describes a software approach for modeling inverter fed induction motor drive using Laboratory Virtual Instrument Engineering Workbench (LabVIEW). The reason behind the selection of LabVIEW software is because of its strong graphical interface, flexibility of its programming language combined with built-in tools designed specifically for test, measurement and control. LabVIEW is generally used in most of the applications for data acquisition, test and control. In this paper, inverter and induction motor are modeled using LabVIEW toolkits. Simulation results are presented and are validated.

Keywords : induction motor, Labview, state model

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